

Inclusive and Equitable Education

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Abstract

Madhesh province is encouraging and supporting the entire community to get education through learning environment. Province not restricting only to children with disabilities but also takes in gender, caste, children with different learning needs, marginalized and economically deprived communities. However, literacy rate of Madhesh province stands 63.5%, whereas the national's literacy rate 76.2% by the census report of Nepal 2021. In the comparison of the national literacy rate of Nepal 77.4%, the men literacy rate is 77.9%, while the women literacy rate is 59.9%, which highlighting a significant gender gap in the Inclusive and Equitable Education (IEE). Also 41.25 % (10-17 years) girls are out of school in Madhesh Province. This is exceptionally high compared to the national average of the total children never going to formal educational school.

The Ministry of Education and Culture (MoEC) has put in place a series of policy frameworks like Provincial education policy, ongoing progression of the Local Education Plan into responsive actions and resources to promote the IEE. In addition, Federal Government of Nepal (GoN) has rolled out their new School Education Sector Plan (SESP), which specifically outlines their approaches to ensuring the IEE within the education system and is working to implement a comprehensive National Equity Strategy.

To ensure greater the IEE, province should strongly apply the regular screening in the classroom, need-based accessible materials and learning corners, tailoring the appropriate pedagogy for the IEE. Also requires the solid instruction to produce the School Improvement Plan (SIP) to develop innovative approaches like Universal Design for Learning and Assessment (UDLA). Province should continue the unique campaign like Mukhyamantri Beti Padhau Beti Bachau to address the problems in the protection, education and empowerment of girls enrollment in the IEE as well as Beti Jindabad campaign initiated by the Ministry of Sports and Social Welfare.

Keywords: equity, inclusive education, learning for all, marginalization